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PARABOLOID QUYOSH KONTSENTRATORLARINI BINOLAR ISSIQLIK SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISHDA QO'LLASH.

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Annotatsiya. Mazkur ishda quyosh paraboloid kontsentratori va issiq pol tizimidan foydalangan holda turar-joy binolarining solishtirma issiqlik sarfini kamaytirish imkoniyatlari o'rganildi. Ishlab chiqilgan matematik modelda paraboloid kontsentrator va issiq pol tizimi birlashtirilgan bo'lib, hisoblashlar MathCAD dasturlash muhitida va Python dasturlash tillarida amalga oshirildi.

Kalit so'zlar: quyosh energiyasi, matematik model, paraboloid quyosh kontsentratori, issiq pol, solishtirma issiqlik sarfi, xarajatlarni qoplash muddati, atrof-muhit va iqlim ko'rsatgichlari.

Kirish. So'nggi asrda shaharlarning rivojlanishi, aholining o'sishi va iqtisodiy rivojlanish natijasida energiya iste'moli global miqyosda sezilarli darajada oshdi [1-3]. Markazlashtirilgan gigavatt miqyosli tizimlarga nisbatan kichik miqyosdagi qayta tiklanadigan energiya tizimlari [4] ko'proq ommalashmoqda.

O'zbekistonda birlamchi energiya resurslarining 40% turar-joy binolarining energiya iste'moliga sarflanadi [5], turar-joy binolarining nisbiy issiqlik iste'moli rivojlangan mamlakatlarga qaraganda 2-4 baravar ko'p [6-7].

Turar-joy binolarining energiya sarfini kamaytirishning bir necha usullari mavjud [8], jumladan an'anaviy energiya manbalarining samaradorligini oshirish va ishlab chiqarilgan issiqlikni iste'molchiga yetkazib berishda minimal issiqlik yo'qotishlariga erishish [9], bino devorlarining issiqlik himoyasini oshirish [10], qurilish elementlarining geometrik va issiqlik parametrlarini optimallashtirish [11] va qayta tiklanadigan energiya manbalaridan foydalanish [12].

Quyosh issiqlik qurilmalari va issiq poldan foydalanib binolarni isitishga mo'ljallangan tizimlarga bag'ishlangan tadqiqot ishlarini uch turga ajratish mumkin [1]: quyosh issiqlik qurilmalariga, bak-akkumulyatoriga va issiq pol tizimiga bag'ishlangan ilmiy tadqiqot ishlari.

Quyosh issiqlik qurilmalariga bag'ishlangan ilmiy-tadqiqot ishlari asosan quyosh issiqlik qurilmasi turi, yuzasi, undagi issiqlik tashuvchining massa sarfini aniqlashga qaratilgan [13].

Bak akkumulyatorga bag'ishlangan ilmiy tadqiqot ishlari undagi issiqlik almashinish jarayonlarini tavsiflash, hajmini aniqlash va issiqlik almashinish jadalligini oshirishga qaratilgan [12,14].

Issiq polga bag'ishlangan tadqiqot ishlarida quvur geometrik o'lchamlari, quvur materiali, quvurlar orasidagi masofa, izolyatsiya qatlamlari turi va issiqlikni akkumulyatsiya qilish imkoniyatlarini aniqlashga qaratilgan. [15-16].

Ko'rib chiqilayotgan obyektning issiqlik xususiyatlarini aniqlash uchun kvazistatik issiqlik balansi modeli ishlatildi. Quyida bino uchun issiqlik balansi tenglamalari mavjud [8]:

$$Q_s + Q_f + Q_{he} = Q_{hl} \quad (1)$$

bunda Q_s - bino ichiga tushadigan quyosh radiatsiyasi; Q_{he} - ichki issiqlik manbalarining issiqlik quvvati; Q_f - issiq polning issiqlik quvvati; Q_{hl} - devorlar, derazalar, eshiklar, pollar, shiftlar va shamollatish orqali issiqlik yo'qotishlari.

1-rasm. Paraboloid quyosh konsentratori, issiqlik akkumulyatori va issiq polga ega binoning isitish tizimi prinsipial sxemasi: 1-konsentrator; 2- bak akkumulyator; 3-bino; 4-issiqlik pol tizimi; 5-nasos; 6- issiq va sovuq suv uchun quvurlar.

Devorlar, derazalar, eshiklar, pollar, shiftlar va shamollatish orqali issiqlik yo'qotishlarini aniqlash matematik ifodasi quyidagicha [17]

$$Q_{hl} = K_{tot}A \cdot HDD, \quad (2)$$

bunda U_{tot} - binoning umumiy issiqlik uzatish koeffitsiyenti, $W/(m^2 \cdot ^\circ C)$; A - binoning tashqi sirtining yuzasi, m^2 ; HDD isitish davrining gradus-sutkasi

$$HDD = (T_i - T_a) \cdot D, \quad (3)$$

bunda T_i - ichki havoning hisobiy harorati, $^\circ C$; T_a - atrof-muhit havosining o'rtacha sutkalik harorati, $^\circ C$; D - istish mavsumining davomiyligi, sutka.

Quyosh nurlanishidan binoga tushadigan issiqlik miqdori [16] da keltirilgan tenglama bilan aniqlanadi. Issiq polning (2-rasm) issiqlik olish quyidagicha tavsiflanadi [18]:

$$Q_f = K_f A_f (T_{aw} - T_{ia}), \quad (4)$$

bunda K_f - issiq pol suyuqligidan ichki havoga issiqlik uzatish koeffitsiyenti; A_f - issiq polning sirt maydoni; T_{aw} - issiq poldagi suyuqlikning o'rtacha harorati; T_{ia} - ichki havo harorati.

Issiq poldan ichki havoga issiqlik uzatish koeffitsiyenti [19]

$$K_f = \left\{ \frac{L}{2\pi\lambda_3} \left[\ln\left(\frac{L}{\pi D_o}\right) + \frac{2\pi d_1}{L} + \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} \frac{G(i)}{i} \right] + \frac{L}{2\pi\lambda_p} \ln\left(\frac{D_o}{D_i}\right) + \frac{1}{h_t} \right\}^{-1}. \quad (5)$$

bunda h_t - pol yuzasidan xona havosiga issiqlik berish koeffitsiyenti; D_o , D_i - quvurning tashqi va ichki diametri; λ_p - quvurning issiqlik o'tkazuvchanlik koeffitsiyenti; d_1 - quvurdan pol sirtigacha masofa; L - quvurlar orasidagi masofa; λ_3 - quvurni o'rab olgan muhit issiqlik o'tkazuvchanlik koeffitsiyenti; $G(i)$ - differensial tenglamalarni analitik usulda yechish orqali olingan koeffitsiyent.

Issiq polning sxemasi: 1- birinchi izolyatsiya qatlami; 2-quvur; 3-beton qatlami; 4- ikkinchi izolyatsiya qatlami.

Issiq polning issiqlik-fizikaviy xususiyatlari [16], [20].

t/r	Qatlam nomi	Qalinligi, mm	Issiqlik o'tkazuvchanlik ko'effitsienti, W/(m·°C)
1. 1	Birinchi izolyatsiya qatlami	3	0.2
2. 2	Quvurlar	2	0.042
3. 3	Beton qatlami	10	1.4
4. 4	Ikkinchi izolyatsiya qatlami	40	0.15

Xulosa. Turar-joy binosi modeli, paraboloid quyosh konsentratori va polni isitish tizimi uchun ishlab chiqilgan barqaror holatdagi matematik modellar birlashtirilib, kompyuter dasturi ishlab chiqildi. Toshkent viloyati iqlimi bo'yicha hisoblashlar o'tkazildi, ko'rib chiqilayotgan turar-joy binosining yillik solishtirma issiqlik iste'moli, xarajatlarni qoplash muddati va ekologik ko'rsatgichlari aniqlandi.

Adabiyotlar ro'yxati.

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“ELEKTRODINAMIKA” BO‘LIMIDAN MUAMMOLI MAZMUNDAGI MASALALARNI TANLASH

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Annotatsiya: Bu maqolada elektrodinamika bo‘limini o‘qitishda muammoli ta‘lim o‘quv jarayoni samaradorligini va o‘quvchining fanga bo‘lgan faolligi va qiziqishini oshirish, muammoli mazmundagi masalalar tanlashda nimalarga e‘tiborini qaratish va muammoli masalalardan na‘munalar keltirilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: Kulon qonuni, Om qonuni, Gauss qonuni, elektrostatik maydon, magnit maydon, zaryadlar.

Аннотация: В данной статье проблемное обучение в преподавании кафедры электродинамики используется для повышения эффективности учебного процесса и повышения активности и интереса студента к науке, на что следует обращать внимание при выборе задач проблемного содержания, приведены примеры представленные проблемные задачи.

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